

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

constRuctive mEtabolic processes For materiaL fLOWs in
urban and peri-urban environments across Europe

Deliverable 7.3

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES REPORT

Due date of deliverable: M36 31/05/2022
Actual submission date: 31/05/2022
Start date of project: 01/06/2019 Duration (36 Months)
Dissemination Level: Public ✓

*This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.*

DELIVERABLE

Work Package	WP7 Dissemination, Exploitation & Sustainability
Deliverable	D7.3 - Communication and Dissemination Activities Report
Task(s)	Task 7.1 Communication and Stakeholders' Engagement [M1-M36] Task 7.2 Dissemination, Clustering and EU-Wide Activities [M1-M36]
Document Name	D7.3 - Communication and Dissemination Activities Report
Due Date	M36: 31 May 2022
Submission Date	M36: 31 May 2022
Dissemination Level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> P - Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential
Deliverable Lead	Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC)
Author(s)	Sara Bosch
Point of Contact	Sara Bosch sara@fablababbcn.org
Reviewers	Thomas van de Sandt
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Working <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final <input type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This report describes the communication activities, as well as the scientific dissemination and clustering activities carried out during the project life cycle.
Keywords	Communication; dissemination; activities; learning; approach
Statement of Originality	This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Revision History

Revision	Date	Author(s)	Organization	Description
D7.3 v0.1	23 November 2021	Sara Bosch	IAAC	<i>Table of Contents</i>
D7.3 v0.2	30 April 2022	Sara Bosch	IAAC	<i>First draft</i>
D7.3 v0.3	14 May 2022	Thomas van de Sandt	AMSTERDAM	<i>Partners first review</i>
D7.3 v1.0	21 May 2022	Sara Bosch	IAAC	<i>Final version by the consortium to be submitted to the EC</i>

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the REFLOW project consortium under EC grant agreement number 820937 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Table of Contents

Table of figures	5
1. Introduction	6
1.1. About REFLOW	6
1.2. REFLOW Vision	6
1.3. About the deliverable	6
1.4. Structure of the report	7
1.5. Connections to the Reflow Framework and other deliverables	7
1.6. Responsibilities	8
1.7. Language	9
2. Communication and dissemination channels and platforms	10
2.1. Channels and platforms	10
2.2. Public platforms	10
Websites	10
Social Media channels	11
YouTube	11
2.3. Internal platforms	11
Action & Event Tracker	11
Pilot Framework	12
Database for journals and conferences	13
3. Communication and dissemination activities	15
3.1. Project website	15
3.1.2. Blog	16
3.1.3. Knowledge Hub	18
3.1.4. Community	18
3.1.4.1. Forum	18
3.1.4.2. Circular Resources	18
3.1.4.3. Best practices database	19
3.1.4.4. Reflow Academy	19
3.2. Newsletters	19
3.3. Webinars	20
3.4. Audiovisual outlets	22
3.5. Social media analytics	25
3.5.1. Twitter	25
3.5.2. Facebook	26

3.5.3. LinkedIn	26
3.6. Press Releases & Media News	27
3.7. Journals and scientific publications	29
3.8. Events & Workshops	30
3.8.1. Types of events	30
3.8.2. Participation	31
3.8.3. Clustering events	31
3.8.4. Organisation	32
3.8.5. REFLOW Final Event	32
4. Performance analysis	34
4.1. KPIs reach	34
4.2. Audience reach	36
5. Annexes	37
5.1. Branding materials	37
5.1.1. Graphic assets	37
5.1.2. Printed materials	41
5.1.3. Communications Map and Process	46

Table of figures

Figure 1: REFLOW Action & Event Tracker

Figure 2. Welcome page of the Pilot Framework Dashboard internal platform

Figure 3. Welcome page of the REFLOW Teams page

Figure 4. Graphic of overview analytics of REFLOW website users (August 1st, 2019 to April 30th, 2022).
Source: Google Analytics

Figure 5. A screenshot of the blog post section with press releases and media news

Figure 6: Mailchimp subscribers via website

Figure 7: YouTube Studio content of the REFLOW channel

Figure 8: YouTube Studio analytics of the REFLOW channel (views)

Figure 9: YouTube Studio analytics of the REFLOW channel (reach)

Figure 10: YouTube Studio analytics of the REFLOW channel (engagement)

Figure 11: Twitter followers the REFLOW profile

Figure 12: Twitter followers the REFLOW profile (impressions and engagement)

Figure 13: Facebook followers the REFLOW page

Figure 14: LinkedIn follower analytics of the REFLOW page

Figure 15: Article published in German in 'Modern Building Technology', April 2022

Figure 16: A screenshot of the final video wrap up

1. Introduction

1.1. About REFLOW

REFLOW is an EU Horizon 2020 research project running from 2019-2022, which aims to enable the transition of European cities towards circular and regenerative practices. More specifically, REFLOW uses Fab Labs and makerspaces as catalysts of a systemic change in urban and peri-urban environments, which enable, visualise and regulate “four freedoms”: free movement of materials, people, (technological) knowledge and commons, in order to reduce materials consumption, maximise multifunctional use of (public) spaces and envisage regenerative practices. The project will provide best practices aligning market and government needs in order to create favourable conditions for the public and private sector to adopt circular economy (CE) practices. REFLOW is creating new CE business models within six pilot cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris and Vejle and assess their social, environmental and economic impact, by enabling active citizen involvement and systemic change to re-think the current approach to material flows in cities.

1.2. REFLOW Vision

A circular and regenerative city in REFLOW represents an urban system with social and business practices which place equal attention to social, environmental and economic impact; where technology is open and represents a central enabler of positive social and environmental change; where the urban system ensures and supports resilience of social and ecological systems; where governance is collaborative and inclusive; where knowledge is shared, and stakeholders are active and involved.

1.3. About the deliverable

The Deliverable 7.3 is part of Work Package 7 (WP7): Dissemination, Exploitation & Sustainability. It describes the communication activities, as well as the scientific dissemination and clustering activities carried out during the project, that is, running from M1 to M36, covering the whole project life cycle. This deliverable has been developed as part of the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, REFLOW, under the Grant Agreement No. 820937.

Communication and dissemination activities have been carefully planned, implemented and regularly monitored during the whole duration of the project. Communication and dissemination activities are carried out according to D7.1 Communication And Dissemination Plan which aims to define and produce the resources, planning and methods that members should use to collaboratively communicate the project, its outcomes and activities to third parties and external stakeholders as a common standard. All project partners have been involved in dissemination and exploitation in order to foster awareness and transfer results for impact, especially in their own countries and in their own communities.

The objective of this WP is to maximise the impact of the project’s results through: i) Communication and dissemination activities at EU and local level for the promotion of the project results to the scientific community as well as the targeted audience (e.g., policy makers, NGOs, Fab labs and citizens) and encouraging

demand for this type of system; ii) Establishment and engagement of external groups third-parties in the validation, evaluation and wider use of the project's results. These groups will include all relevant stakeholders, including local authorities, NGOs, industry actors, and citizens; iii) Formulation of a combined exploitation plan including individual exploitation plans, and a roadmap to take the developed concepts and tools to the market; iv) Development and implementation of credible business models for the commercialisation of the project results; v) Planning of sustainability and wider use of the project's results, through their replication across different cities and regions.

The D7.3 report draws from the following tasks of the WP7 as stated in the Grant Agreement:

Task 7.1 – Communication and Stakeholders' Engagement [M01-M36](Leader: IAAC, Participants: ALL)

Task 7.2 – Dissemination, Clustering & EU-Wide Activities [M01-M36](Leader: IAAC, Participants: ALL)

1.4. Structure of the report

The deliverable is made up of five main parts. These parts are closely intertwined, allowing for one part to coexist with the rest as a two-way interaction:

1. Introduction
2. Communication and dissemination channels and platforms
3. Communication and dissemination activities
4. Performance analysis
5. Annexes

1.5. Connections to the Reflow Framework and other deliverables

This deliverable gives an overview of the communication activities in a quantitative manner, as well as the scientific dissemination and clustering activities carried out during the project. These activities are both crucial and transversal to the whole of the project in multiple ways. Therefore, there are other tasks and deliverables that converge with D7.3, together with a connection to the Reflow Framework.

The Reflow Framework is explained in D1.3 – The Reflow Framework as a supportive model to enable agency and participation of municipalities, SMEs, and citizens' associations in the development of CE practices and governance. Communication and Dissemination activities are not included as a specific section of the Framework but as transversal actions across it such as positioning the REFLOW Framework within CE initiatives and Frameworks of Circular Transitions, targeting audiences, and connecting to the REFLOW Legacy via different formats and types of events (workshops, webinars, conferences, etc); communication initiatives (magazine articles); and Digital initiatives (Forum, Wiki, website, podcast).

The Pilot Framework is a digital content management system for guiding and aligning actors involved in the Circular Transition. The Pilot Cities Framework was created as a system for guiding and aligning, fostering iterative project development, monitoring the progress and boosting knowledge exchange between the cities

and partners. It sets in place a strategy that aims to guide a city in further becoming aware of the opportunities that arise along with the interactions. Its form and structure translate these concepts and aims into a vision for long term use to facilitate support in the replicability of the outcomes, possibly even after the project's lifetime. In REFLOW this has been developed for coordinating communication between Pilot Cities and work packages.

In the first place, there is a clear connection with D7.4 Collaboration with Covenant of Mayors and External Communities Report, which describes many of the activities reported in this deliverable but in a qualitative manner. It describes in more detail how the activities have contributed to the development of the project's results while establishing liaisons with other projects and initiatives for knowledge and innovation transfer. The quantitative results of this report are then explained in a qualitative manner in order to gather feedback and validation, contributing to a further spread of the project and thus the dissemination of its results.

In the second place, this deliverable connects to other deliverables as key target group audiences are involved: D6.3 Capacity Building Toolkit for SMEs, policy makers, NGOs and educationalists to identify, promote, adopt or scale the most promising regenerative and circular practices as they are all key target group audiences stated in D7.1 Communication And Dissemination Plan.

In a similar way, D7.3 can also connect to D5.5 Citizen engagement and Capacity Building, D7.5 Sustainability and Business Plans, and D6.2 Community of Practice. These groups have been an important target audience to get feedback and validation from as end users who benefit from the project outcomes and results, understand the benefits offered by the project, take part in the activities of the project that have been opened for external participation and create synergies to maximise and multiply impact.

In the third place, there is also a connection with D7.2 Data Management Plan, as D7.3 collects and preserves specific data during the project such as project management data (used for internal management of the project and its partners. It includes minutes, mailing lists or protocols among other types of datasets), observational data (captured in real time by researchers or other stakeholders in the consortium, including survey results, images, data collected on public events organised by the project, interviews or statistics generated by the project, among other types of datasets), and derived data, including compiled data from other sources or case studies. It includes data derived from REFLOW's online platforms, databases generated after mining data or statistical analysis, toolkits or reports that use REFLOW's generated data, among other types of data.

All deliverables can be found at the Knowledge Hub: <https://reflowproject.eu/knowledge-hub>.

1.6. Responsibilities

This section generally outlines the responsibilities of all the consortium members in relation to this deliverable. The Institute of Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC) leads the work package (WP7) and has

been in charge of the implementation of the communication and dissemination plan, as decided by the Steering Committee. IAAC has also been responsible for setting up and maintaining the project website, together with the WP leaders and the project coordinator CBS, who have administrator rights to the website.

Therefore, the effective development and implementation of the communication and dissemination activities has required and depended on the joint efforts of all consortium members. Consortium members have been responsible for appropriating the assets provided by IAAC to customise their own communication assets and to reach their specific communities. This has been particularly important because REFLOW has organized events and addressed diverse audiences in six pilot cities (Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris, Vejle) where different languages are spoken and communication cultures vary.

As participants in WP7, pilots and consortium members have been responsible for providing regular and timely updates on their actions, publications and events for communication purposes. This primarily has been done using the "Action & Event Tracker" and the Pilot Dashboard, which members have updated themselves. The Scientific Manager (CBS) has monitored and managed the academic communications under the Database for journals and conferences (see Internal Platforms in Section 2).

It is important to note that every action undertaken within the context of REFLOW has used the appropriate identity and branding which has been provided by IAAC and approved by project leaders CBS (see section 3 Branding materials) including correct reference to the European Union.

1.7. Language

REFLOW communication and dissemination materials have been in UK-style English. However, some materials and other communication activities, specifically those that target local citizens or other stakeholders, have been published in the local language. For example: events taking place at the local Fab Lab or a meeting with local business owners. Translation of texts has been the responsibility of the local pilot coordinator. Additionally, to ensure clarity and continuity throughout external communication, certain terms have been consistently. These terms are defined below:

- The project always refers to REFLOW project in its entirety
- "The consortium" or "the partnership" refers to the entirety of the 27 groups directly participating in the REFLOW project
- "Consortium member(s)" or "consortium partner(s)" (short-hand: "member(s)" / "partner(s)") refers to any of the 27 entities directly participating in REFLOW
- "External partner(s)" refers to non-consortium affiliates e.g. industry associates or groups, local government, etc. like the Ellen MacArthur Foundation
- "stakeholders" or "target audience/group" refers to the groups defined in the GA that REFLOW aims to reach and collaborate with

2. Communication and dissemination channels and platforms

2.1. Channels and platforms

A set of specific communication-dissemination channels and platforms were set up at the beginning of the project based on the principles of:

- Adaptability: to address the project's research themes, actions and stakeholder communities
- Message tailoring: in appropriate language and in the correct channel
- Exploitation of synergies: cross-fertilisation with existing communication and dissemination activities

In this chapter, there is a distinction between the public-facing channels, aimed at communicating and disseminating information, and the internal platforms, used to gather the data of the relevant actions.

2.2. Public platforms

1. Websites

- **REFLOW project website:** <https://reflowproject.eu/> - Please refer to section 3 of this deliverable for more detailed information of the use of it and its analytics.
- **REFLOW Collaborative Governance Toolkit:** <https://governance.reflowproject.eu/> - A platform that helps design and develop collaborative and co-creative paths of discovery and learning towards circular urban systems to external parties.
- **REFLOW Circular Cities Community Forum:** <https://forum.reflowproject.eu/> - an online platform for cities, businesses, and citizens to explore, share and implement circular practices and strategies to tackle urban challenges. By encouraging knowledge exchange and co-creation, we aim to break down information silos and fuel multi-stakeholder collaboration and innovation.
- **Partner websites:** <https://reflowproject.eu/about> - A total of 27 website project partners.
- **Zenodo:** With 55 entries to date, Zenodo has been used along all stages of the project to provide open access to project deliverables, results and databases: <https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=reflow>
- **Knowledge Hub Circle Lab:** With 13 entries, REFLOW has contributed practical examples of the circular economy in one of the main platforms in the industry https://knowledge-hub.circle-lab.com/search?search=reflow&_start=0 - It is part of Circle Economy, a not-for-profit organisation with a mission to accelerate the practical and scalable implementation of the circular economy.

2. Social Media channels

Please refer to section 3 and 4 of this deliverable for more detailed information of the use of it and its reach:

- Twitter: https://twitter.com/REFLOW_project
- Facebook: <https://facebook.com/REFLOWproject/>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/reflow-eu-project/>
- Apple Podcast: <https://podcasts.apple.com/fi/podcast/reflow-podcast/id1545670608>
- Spotify: <https://open.spotify.com/show/0FCmMCpZZBcdpdrEiqmF0>
- Plus the multiple partner and pilot social media channels and hashtags related to the project (e.g. #REFLOWeu)

3. YouTube

Please refer to section 3 and 4 of this deliverable for more detailed information of the use of it and its reach.

Audiovisual outlets with a total of 33 entries for the project:

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC1T49i4A0cH64lpesJoSBdw>

2.3. Internal platforms

1. Action & Event Tracker

The "Action & Event Tracker" is a tool created by IAAC and is the central point of communication between the WP7 leader and the consortium members and pilots. It is accessible via Microsoft Teams with a direct home page button and within the WP7 dedicated folder of SharePoint (see figure 2).

There are 3 sheets in the tracker:

- "Pilot level," where the pilot participants have logged the actions/events specifically related to the pilots
- "Member level", where consortium members have logged actions/events about the project from their own channels
- "Events of interest", which features a list of upcoming conferences and major events that members should keep in mind and which they are also encouraged to add to.

This tracker has helped monitoring short-term the events that pilot and members have "created," "participated in," "hosted," etc. but also in the long-term, as IAAC has used information from the tracker to generate the compiled communication and impact reports to be delivered as part of the project's periodic reports in M18, M24 and final Deliverables. Principally, it measures member participation, assesses whether certain communication vias are responding appropriately and identifies potential partners based on their participation in or creation of events and actions. In the last sheet of the tracker, "Events of interest," features a list of important events that the project recommends members be aware of and participate in, either virtually or physically. IAAC started a list of events and encouraged members to participate in adding events.

						Who participated in the event/activation in numbers? Please add the number of participants for each stakeholder category										
Action (Report)	Medium	Action related to... (it presented the REFLOW project goals to the Amsterdam Business Council -> REFLOW general)	Related Task	Short description (max. 140 characters)	Direct Photo Link: Use link generated for the DMP protocol. To generate the link, store photos in your own WP folder->within the Data and Tools folder->within photos->within a folder titled for the event. Example: C:\Users\user\Documents\WP7\2020\Dissemination\%20Exploitation%20and%20Sustainability\Content\Event%20Photos\7caf1&e=Ryq8f	# Total (incl/Excl)	Industry stakeholders	Fab Labs and maker spaces	Public administrative/Policy makers	EU associations and clusters	Circular economy stakeholders	Research and academia	General public	People from other EU H2020 projects?	People from other co-lab?	
op (hands on)	In-person	Pilot general		6.3 Conference on local makers' projects		150	30	70	20	0	8	30	0	0	0	
	On-line	Specific deliverable update/completion	7.1	Launched communication plan		146	20	5	10	10	20	10	80	5	5	
	On-line	REFLOW global	7.1	CBS Wire news article announcing the development and start of the project												
	On-line	interaction with the Covenant of Mayors (CoM)/ip	7.3	Webinar titled "How to engage citizens in local climate action with online tools?" by the Covenant of Mayors. This v		40				3						
for Research and in-	In-person	interaction with the Covenant of Mayors (CoM)/ip	7.3	Cristiana Parisi from CBS, Lucia Scopelliti from the Municipality of Milan, and the Polifactory team attended the ENoLL EU Research & Innovation Conference workshop within the Open Living Lab Days in Thessaloniki. The workshop was organized by our PO Emanuela de Menna and h												
	On-line	Other	7.1	general news about project												
	In-person	REFLOW global	7.1	Over 2 days, we will explore future scenarios of blockchain technology as a solution for the grand challenges faced by society and industry as well as discuss the risks and pitfalls it may pose. Cristiana Parisi (PCO) will moderate the panel discussion "Can technology advance sustainab												
	On-line	REFLOW global	7.1	General info on the project												
istry of Industry, Bu-	In-person	REFLOW global	7.3	Together with front running companies, decision makers and experts you will be part of exploring how cities can su		100										
	On-line	REFLOW global		Description of REFLOW project		100										
	On-line	REFLOW global		Use and added REFLOW launch press release		100										
	On-line	Pilot general		MCS release on first year of project		100										
	On-line	Pilot general		MCS release on Berlin pilot entering an intensified phase		100										
	In-person	interaction with the Covenant of Mayors (CoM)/ip	7.3	The Summit will showcase examples of how cities are already delivering on their strong commitments and accelerate the bold climate solutions needed for a sustainable, healthier, resilient and inclusive future. All the events that Cristiana participated in can be found below												
	In-person	REFLOW global	6.3	Workshop on climate change and city strategy for zero-emissions		50	10	5	30	5						
	In-person	REFLOW global	7.1	IAAC's Pilsener Open night stop featured a stand on REFLOW and a drawing activity for participants to re-imagin		300										
	In-person	Pilot general		The CBS team is coming to Vale to see the objects produced: https://studios.stir.ac.uk/news/REFLOW/shane/		5										

Figure 1: REFLOW Action & Event Tracker

2. Pilot Framework

The Pilot Framework Dashboard hosts the section "Communications Update WP7", which has allowed for a qualitative gathering of data related to communication and dissemination activities exclusive to each pilot. It has private internal access for pilots via the URL: <https://cities.reflowproject.eu/login>.

The "Communications Update WP7" main function has been related to content creation: As the WP7 leader, IAAC has referred to the update when building content such as blog posts and social media messages. An image of the website homepage (Pilot Framework) is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2. Welcome page of the Pilot Framework Dashboard internal platform

3. Database for journals and conferences

The database for journals and conferences is also a tool created by IAAC in order to gather scientific journal publications and paper presentations dissemination information related to pilots and members of the project. It is accessible via Microsoft Teams with a direct home page button and within the WP7 dedicated folder of SharePoint. An image of Teams homepage with direct access to both the Journals and Conferences database and the Action & Event tracker is shown in Figure 2:

Figure 3. Welcome page of the REFLOW Teams page

3. Communication and dissemination activities

Please note an interpretation of the following numbers across all platforms and social media channels related to benchmarks and KPI's is provided in Chapter 4.

3.1. Project website

The REFLOW project website (<https://reflowproject.eu/>) is the primary hub for project communication and a portal for dissemination of key project deliverables. A platform for Pilot Cities to get inspiration and knowledge both from within the project and outside of it. The website was set up at the beginning of the project and went online in August 2019, therefore Google analytics data is available from then.

Figure 4. Graphic of overview analytics of REFLOW website users (August 1st, 2019 to April 30th, 2022). Source: Google Analytics

The REFLOW project website is a key tool for communicating information about project activities, news and events, as well as to convey results to a wide range of target groups. The website was created in line with the visual identity and is continuously maintained by IAAC with contributions from all partners.

The website contains different sections in order to communicate and disseminate information about the project resources (publications, newsletters, videos, deliverables, etc.), and other useful links, mainly:

- About introductory section

- Pilots information
- Knowledge Hub for project related resources and deliverables
- Community section (with the Forum, Circular Resources, Best practices database, Reflow Academy, Case studies)
- Blog space for articles, news and press releases
- Events area with a special emphasis on project and clustering events
- Contact information

3.1.2. Blog

A total of 60 blog posts have been published and divided into different tag categories in order to make the information easier to find and navigate amongst the different posts:

- Circular in the news: a section dedicated to press releases, media and public announcement communication
- Learning nugget: a curious set of interesting news related to the project and the circular economy
- Meet the reflowers: the space to get to know each pilot and their activities
- Updates: general updates related to the project and its pilots
- Webinars: a dedicated section that explains the key take-aways of each of the project webinars

Figure 5. A screenshot of the blog post section with press releases and media news

3.1.3. Knowledge Hub

The REFLOW Knowledge Hub is where you can find methods and resources about the process of becoming a circular, regenerative city with the project. Being developed over the lifetime of the project and based on project outputs and building blocks, the Hub organises resources in a four-step circular design thinking transition process: understand, define, make, release. The Knowledge Hub is divided into the following different subsections and tags that help navigating the different types of information:

- Capacity building
- Communication
- Business & Society
- Governance and Urban Strategies
- Materials engineering
- Pilots
- Technology

3.1.4. Community

This section of the website is the platform for cities, businesses, and citizens to explore, share and implement circular practices and strategies to tackle urban challenges. By encouraging knowledge exchange and co-creation, we aim to fuel multi-stakeholder collaboration and innovation. This section includes the Circular Economy Starter Kit in order to explain REFLOW's journey towards circular and regenerative cities. The section is subdivided into the following four subsections:

3.1.4.1. Forum

The REFLOW Forum is a community of practice in the form of an online platform for cities, businesses, and citizens to explore, share and implement circular practices and strategies to tackle urban challenges. By encouraging knowledge exchange and co-creation, we aim to break down information silos and fuel multi-stakeholder collaboration and innovation. The Forum is divided into the following different categories that help contributing the different types of information:

- Knowledge transfer: A space to share innovative activities, business models, reports, policies that support regenerative and circular cities.
- Co-creation: Ask if the community can support you in solving barriers to implementing circular solutions
- Circular Resources: Find additional pedagogical resources, research insights and circular toolkits to help you on your transition journey.

3.1.4.2. Circular Resources

In order to enhance the exchange of knowledge and knowledge transfer, the Circular Resources dedicated section of the website is used to find relevant online material on the Circular Economy. The section is subdivided into subsections in order to facilitate finding the information with external audiences:

- Reports & Publications
- Online courses
- Podcasts

3.1.4.3. Best practices database

This database draws from external sources and examples in order to enrich the transition to a circular city beyond the project. The different categories include:

- Business models
- Circular materials, including textile, plastic,
- Citizen engagement
- City policies

3.1.4.4. Reflow Academy

The Academy is for anyone interested in learning with REFLOW, including:

- Case studies
- Podcasts
- Ecourses
- Masterclasses

3.2. Newsletters

A total of 620 subscribers:

Campaigns

Current audience

Your audience has **620** contacts.

Figure 6: Mailchimp subscribers via website

The project sent a total of 18 newsletters across the project (over the 2/year KPI):

- March 20th, 2020: <https://mailchi.mp/c9391e3c709f/reflow-project-newsletter>
- July 20th, 2020: <https://mailchi.mp/89ae5f29a77d/reflow-toolkit-for-circular-cities-in-here>
- November 3rd, 2020: <https://mailchi.mp/05a220e6ba00/reflow-toolkits-for-circular-cities-in-here-2624089>
- June 1st, 2021: <https://us2.campaign-archive.com/?u=d67ba8deb34a23a222ec4eb8a&id=2304b15519>
- June 29th, 2021: <https://us2.campaign-archive.com/?u=d67ba8deb34a23a222ec4eb8a&id=2304b15519>
- September 28th, 2021: <https://mailchi.mp/3b875298c760/discover-a-new-collaborative-toolkit>
- November 17th, 2021: <https://mailchi.mp/a37a09ea26c5/join-the-eugreenweek-partner-event-2624265>
- December 3rd, 2021: <https://mailchi.mp/82b5121e0db5/join-the-eugreenweek-partner-event-2624281>
- January 12th, 2022: <https://mailchi.mp/0652ac1114cb/join-the-eugreenweek-partner-event-2624285>
- February 16th, 2022: <https://mailchi.mp/reflowproject.eu/event-data-enabled-circular-cities>
- March 2nd, 2022: <https://mailchi.mp/reflowproject.eu/final-event>
- March 15th, 2022: <https://mailchi.mp/reflowproject.eu/final-event-academy>
- March 21st, 2022: <https://mailchi.mp/reflowproject.eu/last-chance>
- April 27th: <https://mailchi.mp/reflowproject.eu/new-project-assets>

3.3. Webinars

REFLOW has translated the deliverables published on the project website and Zenodo into 3 interactive and timely webinars that have allowed explaining the outcomes of the project from a communication perspective. At the same time, they have been allowed to expand the project to external collaborators who work in relevant businesses, institutions and organisations of the industry.

The first webinar was also selected to be part of the EU Green Week Partner event in the 2021 edition (<https://ec.europa.eu/environment/archives/greenweek2021/index.html>), the key event in the EU environment policy calendar. This annual opportunity to debate and discuss European environmental policy attracts policymakers, leading environmentalists, stakeholders and other interested parties from across Europe and the globe.

	Title	Topic	Keynote speaker	Pilot speaker	External speaker	Link to video	Link to article
Webinar 1: 10 June 2021	Urban metabolism	Material flow	Liz Corbin - Metabolic	Ann Louise S lot - Vejle Pilot	Simon Clement - ICLEI	https://youtu.be/enBeaM_sjAU	https://reflowproject.eu/blog/urban-

	for circular cities	analysis (WP3)					metabolism-for-circular-cities-key-stakeaways/
Webinar 2: 1 December 2021	Tools to steer the transition	Collaborative Governance (WP4)	Valentina Frosini - P2p lab	Andrea Patrucco - Milan Pilot	Claudia Alessio - Circle Economy	https://youtu.be/Ln5W-GkBcTA	https://reflowproject.eu/blog/key-takeaways-from-reflow-second-webinar/
Webinar 3 - 23 February 2022	Data-enabled circular cities	Digital solutions (WP2)	Adam Burns - Dyne	Stefano Bocconi - Amsterdam Pilot + Enrico Bassi - Milan Pilot	Stefan Sipka - European Policy Centre	https://youtu.be/BIMyOM5msgA	https://reflowproject.eu/blog/key-takeaways-from-the-data-enabled-circular-cities-webinar/

Figure 7: YouTube Studio content of the REFLOW channel

3.4. Audiovisual outlets

Analytics:

- 25 direct subscribers
- 32 videos in total
- Over 1,000 views
- Over 6,800 impressions

Last video wrap up of the final event included a total of 10 interviews to all pilots and several partners involved:

<https://youtu.be/G0JA4mALJ9s>

Figure 8: YouTube Studio analytics of the REFLOW channel (views)

Figure 9: YouTube Studio analytics of the REFLOW channel (reach)

Figure 10: YouTube Studio analytics of the REFLOW channel (engagement)

3.5. Social media analytics

3.5.1. Twitter

With 560+ followers and 367 tweets since September 2019.

Figure 11: Twitter follows the REFLOW profile

Figure 12: Twitter followers the REFLOW profile (impressions and engagement)

3.5.2. Facebook

The REFLOW Facebook page has 450+ followers.

Page	Total Page Likes	From last week	Posts This Week	Engagement This Week
YOU 1 REFLOW EU Project	452	▲ 100%	0	2

Figure 13: Facebook followers the REFLOW page

3.5.3. LinkedIn

The LinkedIn page has a total of 700+ followers.

Figure 14: LinkedIn follower analytics of the REFLOW page

3.6. Press Releases & Media News

REFLOW has published a total of 7 press releases at a project level, and 2 at a pilot level, with relevant and newsworthy information targeted at media. The content is suitable for journalists including key text and high resolution visual resources about the project, the consortium, and the pilots:

- <https://reflowproject.eu/blog/reflow-h2020-project-launch/>
- <https://reflowproject.eu/blog/cities-circular-action-plan-launched/>
- <https://reflowproject.eu/blog/reflow-project-finished-its-first-year/>
- <https://reflowproject.eu/blog/best-practice-example/>
- <https://reflowproject.eu/blog/reflow-academy-launches-the-project-webinar-series/>
- <https://reflowproject.eu/blog/registration-to-the-reflow-final-event-is-open/>
- <https://reflowproject.eu/blog/an-outlook-on-circularity/>

Relevant external mentions Covenant of Mayors:

- Article about the REFLOW case studies: <https://www.eumayors.eu/news-and-events/news/1957-reflow-project-5-sustainable-and-circular-cities-projects-case-studies.html>

- The REFLOW five case studies: https://www.eumayors.eu/en/?option=com_attachments&task=download&id=1360
- Support > Library section of the Covenant of Mayors website: <https://www.eumayors.eu/news-and-events/news/1957-reflow-project-5-sustainable-and-circular-cities-projects-case-studies.html>

Relevant media mentions:

- Take to News: <https://taketonews.com/in-this-way-the-city-mobilizes-various-actors-for-a-circular-textile-industry>
- Fashion United: <https://fashionunited.nl/nieuws/business/van-workshops-tot-swapshops-en-green-deals-dit-deed-reflow-de-afgelopen-jaren-voor-een-circulair-textielsysteem-in-amsterdam/2022042253309>
- TGA Praxis: <https://www.tga-praxis.de/fachmagazin/fachartikel/das-berliner-abwaerme-radar-foerdert-technologien-fuer-die-waermewende.html>

Figure 15: Article published in German in 'Modern Building Technology', April 2022

3.7. Journals and scientific publications

A total of 6 publications have been released in conferences and also articles in journals:

- "Assessing and managing the impact of COVID-19: a study of six European cities participating in a circular economy project". Authors: Cristiana Parisi and Justyna Bekier. Journal: Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal. 13/07/2021. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/AAAJ-08-2020-4837/full/html>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

- "Validating collaborative practices for urban circular economy: the design perspective". Authors: De Salvo Veronica, Carraro Martina, Bianchini Massimo, Maffei Stefano. Journal: *TECHNE | Journal of Technology for Architecture and Environment*, Vol. 22. 31/10/2021. <https://oaj.fupress.net/index.php/techne/issue/view/662/206>
- "Reflow: Zero Knowledge Multi Party Signatures with Application to Distributed Authentication". Author: Denis Roio, Alberto Ibrisevic, Andrea D'Intino. Journal: *arXiv.org*. 30/05/2021. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2105.14527>
- "Emergence and Stabilisation of Performance Accounts for the Circular Economy: The Role of Representations". Author: Justyna Bekier, Andrea Beye, Cristiana Parisi. *Nordic Science and Technology Studies Conference 2021: STS and the Future as a Matter of Collective Concern*. 20 to 21 May 2021. <https://research.cbs.dk/en/publications/emergence-and-stabilization-of-performance-accounts-for-the-circu>
- "Food markets as circular digital hub. Prototyping new enabling ICT infrastructure solutions and city-scale data practices for urban food systems". Author: M. Bianchini; S. Maffei. *International Journal of Food Design*. Submitted in August 2021. Article accepted and peer-reviewed, now ready to be published in 2022
- "Measuring and reporting sustainability performance through Social Return on Investment: An empirical analysis". Author: Cristiana Parisi in Nijkamp and Fusco Girard (Eds.) *Measuring and Controlling Sustainability: Spanning Theory and Practice*, Franco Angeli (Milan). Under review

3.8. Events & Workshops

3.8.1. Types of events

During almost half of the duration of the 3 years project, some events were cancelled or postponed due to COVID-19 restrictions. Despite this, a large number and varied type of events were handled by pilots and partners, either organising them or attending them to represent and/or explain REFLOW, namely:

- Workshops
- Conferences
- Webinars
- Exhibitions
- Showcases
- Live sessions
- Pecha-Kucha presentations
- Educational programmes
- Roundtables
- Fair Trades
- Fab City Camp
- Podcasts

3.8.2. Participation

REFLOW members participated with the presentation of the project or the attendance to over 30 conferences mostly across the different years of the project, including:

- Dresden Nexus Conference: Circular Economy in a Sustainable Society
- Plastic Free World Conference & Expo
- BEYOND 2020 - World sustainable built environment conference
- The European Recycling Conference ERC
- 5th International Conference on New Business Models
- IS4CE Inaugural International Conference for the Circular Economy
- FabX Live
- Cities and Citizens Energy Forum
- Interdisciplinary Circular Economy Conference 2020
- World Circular Economy Forum
- 9th European Conference on Sustainable Cities and Towns - ICLEI
- City's future summit
- Distributed Fab City Summit
- CE Hotspot
- Smart City Expo World Congress
- LOOPS#3: A discussion with CLAIM and PlastiCircle!
- Empowering the circular bioeconomy through the EU Green Deal
- Trade, Resource Extraction & Circular Economy
- Circular Economy: Are we delivering?
- Circular business models at the heart of the EU's new Circular Economy Action Plan
- Circular Economy Joint Programming in Europe
- Circular Economy and Private Sector Development: a Learning Series
- MeetingPack Congress 2021: Barrier packaging solutions in the circular economy
- EU Green Week
- 3rd International Workshop on Smart Circular Economy
- Transylvanian Clusters International Conference 2021: Reflow side-event
- World Circular Economy Forum
- Circular Economy Hotspot Catalonia
- TIM 2021 Physics Conference

3.8.3. Clustering events

Clustering with other EU and sister projects with REFLOW facilitates sharing and learning opportunities to transfer knowledge across the multitude of projects running in parallel to REFLOW. Furthermore, clustering provides the opportunity to gain support, traction, and help on specific challenges from other projects facing the same. Collaborative opportunities through workshops, webinars, and surveys and more can also arise from clustering activities. WP7 has contributed to the organisation of these clustering events via social media promotion and communication and dissemination, organisational meetings, and with the provision of experts.

Some examples of clustering events include:

- **Making it Circular Challenge Competition:** with Pop Machina (special event collaboration): with over 140 participants and over 130 views after the live event: <https://youtu.be/e4YddBJ3tyU>
- **Webinar LOOPS 2.0 #7:** a discussion with REFLOW and CityLoops Veltha: with over 180 views after live event <https://youtu.be/fxkcx74MlnY>
- **The Fab Foundation event:** How maker spaces and Fab Labs can accelerate the transition to circular cities. With over 115 views after the live event <https://youtu.be/MCh5AwIU4bE>
- **EU Green Week:** contributing to the programme with a partner event for the 2021 edition <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/archives/greenweek2021/index.html>
- **United Nations Sustainable Development goals:** e.g. The Berlin pilot is mainly targeting the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals: (6) Clean water and sanitation, (7) Affordable and clean energy, (11) Sustainable cities and communities and (13) Climate action: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
- **Vejle's Resilience Strategy** – born in the context of the city's involvement within the [100 Resilience Cities initiative](#) – and the more recent [Climate Plan](#) set the framework for the specific circular experiments developed in REFLOW, where the circular economy is essentially understood as a driver for environmental and social resilience

3.8.4. Organisation

The REFLOW project organised and/or hosted a total 140 events at a pilot level and a total of 26 at a member level, according to their reporting tools available both on the Pilot Dashboard and the Events Tracker. Target audiences included Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research), Industry, Civil Society, General Public Policy Makers, Media, Investors, Customers and Others. These forms of communication created opportunities to present the project to a wider audience, distribute project materials, and to contribute to mechanisms of public policy. Examples of the use of the visual identity of the project to promote the project are illustrated in the annexes. The two-day conference called “Circular Cities Conference: Reflow and Beyond” was the last event organised by the project.

3.8.5. REFLOW Final Event

REFLOW Final event: The final event was prepared and organised by Copenhagen Business School (CBS), in collaboration with IAAC for co-organisation, marketing and communication, and the remaining project partners for development of content. The overarching aim of the conference was to share the results of the project and insights about key methodologies used in Reflow, as well as to contribute to the public discussion on circularity in cities.

It was a two-day conference called “Circular Cities Conference: Reflow and Beyond”: the first day was online (March 30th, 2022) and the second at CBS premises (March 31st, 2022).

The first day focused on the stakeholders who interact and collaborate for the circular and regenerative transitions. Eighteen speakers participated in the discussion in five different sessions on governance, business, policy, citizens and research.

The second day was focused on the project's results, learnings, and impacts and 34 speakers engaged in a fruitful discussion on how to implement and scale circular solutions.

A total of 120 participants attended to the in-person meeting in Copenhagen with 51 members of the Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research), 20 Industry, 5 Civil Society, 4 General Public, 9 Policy Makers, 3 Media, and 1 Investor, while online viewers will continue benefit and learn via the multiple videos made available in a special YouTube channel playlist:

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLdmH9TJqxIDSihLRh1N13g3K0zW_JZ1w.

A final video of the project in order to showcase the final event and outcomes of the REFLOW project. Due to COVID-19, the interview recording of REFLOW members was postponed to the next physical meeting with the higher attendance such as the final event. IAAC interviewed 10 relevant people of the project at a management and implementation level, including representatives of the pilots, about the REFLOW outcomes and outputs, tools and platforms (Botto, Reflow OS, Collaborative Governance Toolkit), key milestones of the project and the REFLOW impact and legacy in the world.

The final wrap up video has been published in the REFLOW YouTube channel:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G0JA4mALJ9s>

Figure 16: A screenshot of the final video wrap up

4. Performance analysis

4.1. KPIs reach

All of the project KPIs established for WP7 have been reached before the end of the project.

Channel	Target Group(s)	KPIs	Target value in GA (over project life)	Status	Reasonable target reached (yes/no)
Website	General public	No. of unique visitors, No. of page views Avg. duration visits	25,000 50,000 2 min	29,232 82,585 01:45	Yes, mostly exceed
Social Media	General public	No. of followers, No. of posts, Avg. post reach	2,000 by M36 1/week 200	2,350+ 3/week 200+	Yes, exceeded
Content delivery platform (e.g. YouTube, SlideShare)	General public	No. of channels, No. of contents uploaded	Project present in at least one delivery platform, with a minimum of 3 posts per year	REFLOW project x 31 +FabXLive video presentation in the Fab City Summit	Yes, exceeded
Local media (TV, newspapers, radio, magazines)	General public	No. of appearances	One appearance per year per participating country	3	No, but compensated with extra content

Leaflets, brochures, newsletters	Local/regional/national authorities, EU cities, industrial companies, SMEs, Fab Labs, scientific community	No. of stakeholders reached	5,000 2 newsletters/ per year = a total of 6	10,000+ 6 newsletters per year = a total of 18	Yes, exceeded (3 times more)
Press releases	Industrial companies, SMEs, Fab Labs, general public	No. of press releases issued	3 press release/year	7 + extra content (newsletter, audiovisual outlets)	Yes
Workshops, events	Scientific/ research community	No. of workshops organised, No. of attendees	Two sessions per year in the context of a major congress, conference, event, with a minimum 200 attendees	+FabX conference +Fab City Summit +Smart City Expo World Congress +Maker Faire Paris and Rome editions +Maison Objet	Yes, exceeded
Presentations	Industrial companies, SMEs, Fab Labs, local/national authorities, EC, cities	No of presentations performed	80 (by the end of the project)	250+	Yes, exceeded

4.2. Audience reach

According to the data gathered throughout the project lifetime, more than 500,000 people were reached at a pilot level and over 7,000 people were reached at a member level both with the organisation of events and at a participatory level.

Gathering the exact data by category was possible with the organisation of the event since the project was in charge of asking the type of audience at the time of the registration. Taking this into account, this is the estimated number of people reached through the communication and dissemination and activities by category with the activities and events hosted or created by the REFLOW project at a pilot and member level:

Category	Estimated number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	1,000
Industry	2,500
Civil Society	5,000
General Public	10,000
Policy Makers	500
Media	500
Investors	100
Customers	-
Others	1,000

5. Annexes

5.1. Branding materials

5.1.1. Graphic assets

- Logos variations

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

- GIFs

A large dark blue rectangular graphic containing the text "FINDINGS" in large, bold, orange capital letters at the top and "NEW EVENT" in large, bold, orange capital letters at the bottom. The graphic is decorated with several white and green icons: a large white curved arrow on the left, a green circular arrow icon with the word "Reflow" in white in the center, a white zig-zag arrow pointing down on the right, and a large white circular arrow on the bottom right. A smaller green circular arrow icon with the word "Reflow" in white is also located in the bottom left corner of the graphic.

- **Zoom backgrounds**

5.1.2. Printed materials

- Flyers

REFLOW

Co-creating
circular flows

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

The transition to a circular and regenerative economy requires radical new synergies, collaborations and strategic alliances between a range of actors, as well as new forms of infrastructuring collaboration.

REFLOW is an EU H2020 funded project that seeks to transform urban material flows, **co-create** and **test regenerative solutions** at business, governance, and citizen levels to create a resilient circular economy.

The project combines the expertise of 25+ European project partners spanning municipalities, scientific and research institutions, technology providers, design & grassroots organisations, and small- and medium-sized enterprises. The six pilot cities are **Velje, Paris, Amsterdam, Cluj-Napoca, Berlin** and **Milan**, and are focusing on plastics, wood, textile, energy, wastewater heat, and food.

Open call for co-creators

We are developing and testing solutions together.
Take part in the co-creation process with us and:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industry Stakeholders - Fab Labs & Makerspaces - Public Administrations - Circular Economy Stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers & Academia - The General Public & Civic Society - Policy Makers
--	---

Reflowproject.eu

@REFLOWproject

@REFLOW_project

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

5.1.3. Communications Map and Process

miro

